

RESEARCH ON DRYING PUMPKIN

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Pumpkin is an annual crop belonging to the pumpkin family. Native to North and South America. 3 types are popular - pumpkin with a large fruit (potato pumpkin), butternut squash (mummy), pumpkin with thick and hard skin (common pumpkin) [1-8].

Pumpkin is a heat-loving, light-loving plant that grows well in moist and fertile soil. Low resistance to high temperatures and drought. The root is 2 m long. The stem lies and grows together. The leaves (depending on the variety) are large, drooping, with curls in the leaf axils. The flowers are bisexual, large, yellow, pollinated by insects [3, 9-11].

The fruit contains 15-18% dry matter, 4-15% sugar, ascorbic acid, carotene, thiamine, riboflavin, nitrogen compounds, pectin substances, and 20-40% oil in the seed. Its seeds and oil are used in pharmaceuticals, the food industry, etc. Currently, 9 varieties of pumpkin are grown in Uzbekistan. Today, pumpkin products grown in our country are exported to countries such as Austria, Germany, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, UAE, Russia, Czech Republic [3, 12-17].

Common varieties of pumpkin in Uzbekistan:

Palav Kadu 268. Mid-season variety, growing season – 114-116 days. The vines are medium-sized, the length of the main stem is 3-4 m, there are many lateral branches and leaves. The fruit is long, slightly smaller and more expanded from the side. Sometimes slightly arched. The sides are thinner than the top of the fruit, weight 3.1-3.8 kg, the peel is reddish-yellow, hard. There are small reddish bubbles on the surface, and when ripe the fruit is covered with light brown, small dark green, and sometimes pink mesh spots. The pulp is reddish-yellow, soft, medium sweet, tasting score 4.0. Productivity 25-30 t/ha [3].

Kashgarskaya 1644. The variety is mid-season, the growing season is 117-120 days. The vines are medium, the length of the main stem is 2.5-3.0 m, the leaf is medium, the flower is large, yellow. The fruit is long, blunt on both sides, thinned in the middle, sometimes pear-shaped, weighing 3.8-4.7 kg. The skin is

orange, thin, slightly rough, with dark green ribs. The pulp is reddish-yellow, thick and dense. Dry matter content 7.6%, sugar content 4.7%. Productivity 35-38 t/ha [3].

Spanish 73. Late ripening variety. The growing season is 117-130 days. The branches are very large, the length of the main trunk is 5-7 m or more. The flower is large, orange. The fruit is flat-round, segmented, gray-green, the length of the fruit strip is 6-7 cm, the sides of the fruit are thickened, very hard, weight 3.3-4.4 kg. The pulp is yellow, dense, sweet, tasting score 5.0 points. Dry matter content 14.7%, sugar 12.0%, carotene 70 mg/%. Productivity 25-30 t/ha. Stores very well in winter [3].

Shirintoy. Late ripening variety. The growing season is 135 days. The fruit is elongated-cylindrical, the peel and pulp are orange, rough, the flesh is dense, the fruit weight is 2.5 kg. Tasting score 5.0 points. The seed chamber is small, the seeds are small and dense. Productivity 25-27 t/ha. Suitable for transportation, disease resistant. [3].

Ferro F1. Hybrid of the Dutch company "Rijk Zwaan". Entered into the State Register in 2016. Mid-season variety. The branches are of medium length, the leaf shape is conical, the color is green, large, the back side of the leaf is covered with gray dust. The shape of the fruit is oval-round, the color of the peel is dark green, the surface of the fruit is even and smooth. The color of the pulp is light yellow, the seeds are medium in size. The weight of the fetus is 3.1 kg. Taste 4.5 points. The growing season is 108 days. Productivity in 2014-2015, the average yield per hectare at the Chinoz variety trial was 64.2 t/ha, at the Tashkent variety trial - 20.5 t/ha. Convenient to transport over long distances. Resistant to diseases [3].

Bakhodir. Variety Research Institute of Plant Growing. Entered into the State Register in 2019. The fruit is large, weighing up to 12-15 kg, round-elliptical in shape, yellow in color. When fresh, it is used for processing and as feed [1].

Butler F1. Hybrid of the Dutch company Gebroeders Bakker Zaahteelt en Zaahandel B.V. Included in the State Register since 2021. The fruit is pear-shaped, hard, weighing 1.5-3 kg, length 26-28 cm. The color of the peel is yellow, the color of the pulp is bright yellow. The vegetable is stored for a long time. Designed for growing in open areas and as a repeat crop. Stems are semi-branched [1].

The most popular and best varieties of pumpkin are presented depending on their species, i.e. large-fruited, hard-barked and nutmeg. Common pumpkin varieties in Belarus [18]:

Cucurbita maxima "Ulibka". The variety is early ripening (85-90 days from germination to harvest), a bush plant, forms up to 6 short shoots. The leaf is light green with a yellow mosaic. Forms up to 8-10 spherical fruits weighing 0.8-1.2 kg (maximum - up to 2 kg) of light orange (according to other sources, bright orange) color with white (light) faintly noticeable stripes. The pulp is thick, bright orange, crispy, sweet, slightly juicy, with a melon aroma. It has increased cold resistance, produces a crop in any weather conditions, and is resistant to drought. Portion type, perfect for cooking in the microwave. It stores well, the fruits last until March [18].

Kroshka. The variety is mid-season or mid-late (115-125 days from full germination to technical ripeness). The plant is of medium strength, the main vine is long. The fruit is flat-round, smooth, weighing 2.5-3.0 kg, light gray in color, yield up to 7.0 kg per m². The pulp is bright orange, thick, dense, brittle, low-juiced (according to other sources, juicy), sweet, with a high content of dry substances and sugars, taste is good or excellent. Can be used raw in salads and for all types of traditional culinary processing. It is valued for its stable yield, uniformity and portion size of fruits, resistance to anthracnose, excellent keeping quality (the consumer qualities of the fruits remain until March) and suitability for transportation [18].

Cucurbita Volzhskaia seraia (Volga gray 92). The variety is mid-season (102-121 days from full germination to harvesting). The plant is long-climbing (up to 8 m), powerful, with large kidney-shaped leaves. The fruit is slightly or moderately flattened, slightly segmented or smooth, weighing 6.3-9.0 kg. The color is light gray and greenish-gray, without a pattern. The bark is elastic and leathery. Productivity – up to 15.0 kg per m². The pulp is yellow and cream in color, 4-4.5 cm thick, medium density, sweet. The taste is good. The variety is resistant to crop diseases, drought-resistant, has high shelf life of fruits during storage, and good transportability. It has good taste, nutritional and dietary qualities [18].

Marble (mramornaya). The variety is medium late (from germination to harvest - 130-140 days). The plants are long-climbing and powerful. The fruits are flattened, with an average

weight of 4-5 kg, with a wrinkled-segmented surface. The color of the bark is gray and dark gray, with light gray mottling and stripes. The pulp is deep orange, dense, thick, crispy, sweet. In terms of taste, the variety is also among the leaders, not inferior to nutmeg pumpkins. Suitable for any traditional pumpkin dishes. One of the best table varieties for long-term storage in winter. Does not lose consumer qualities until March inclusive [18].

Cucurbita pepo (Winter sweet). The variety is late-ripening (108-140 days from germination to harvest). The plant is medium- to long-climbing, up to 5-6 m long. The fruits are round-oval, flattened, weakly segmented, tuberculate, thin-barked. The pulp is orange, thick, dense, sweet. Weighing 4.5-6.5 kg (maximum up to 7 kg). Productivity up to 30 kg per m². The variety has high transportability, keeping quality, is resistant to anthracnose and powdery mildew, drought-resistant, has a stable yield and high quality pulp. Does not accumulate nitrates. Intended for dietary and baby food, processing into juices [18].

Hundred pound. The variety is medium late (112-138 days from full germination to fruit harvest). The plant is long-climbing, of medium thickness. The length of the main stem is up to 7 m. The fruits are spherical and short-oval. The surface of the fruit is smooth or slightly segmented, lumpy. The weight of the fetus is 10-20 kg or more (up to 50 kg). The surface color is pink, yellow, orange and gray. The bark is thin and flexible. The pulp is cream and yellow, loose, 4-5 cm thick. The seeds are large, white. Productivity up to 15.0 kg per m². The taste is good, the keeping quality is good, it is a grade for table and feed purposes. Value of the variety: resistance to fruit rot, powdery mildew and bacteriosis, large-fruited, high yield. Recommended for consumption fresh (for salads) and processed, for making juices, filling for pies [18].

Butternut. The variety is early ripening (ready for harvest 80-90 days after sowing). The plant is climbing, the length of the lash reaches 3 meters. The fruits are shaped like a pear or a guitar, yellowish-orange in color, weighing 1.5-3 kg. Under the thin, hard skin there is a rich orange pulp, an original sweet taste with nutty notes, loose, tender, juicy, with a light nutmeg aroma and a huge amount of vitamins and important elements. The seeds are located in the lower (wide) part of the fruit. Excellent for baby and diet food, boiling, frying and baking, as well as a side dish for meat and fish dishes and fresh freezing. Dessert

dishes are also prepared from pumpkin: cakes, pies, candied fruits. Suitable for long-term storage [18].

Matilda F1. Mid-early hybrid (100-110 days from germination to harvesting the first fruits). The plant is climbing, vigorous. Large pear-shaped fruits, mustard yellow in color, slightly ribbed, with orange dense flesh and a small seed chamber. The taste is excellent. The average fruit weight is 4-5 kg, yield is 7-9.5 kg per m² (maximum up to 14-15 kg). Retains excellent taste both fresh and with any method of thermal processing. Resistant to low and high temperatures (stress-resistant). Transportable. The fruits retain commercial quality for 4 months after picking [18].

Muscat de Provence (Muscat de Provence). The variety is medium late (115-125 days). The plant is climbing, of medium thickness. The main lash is of average length - 4-5 meters. The fruits are flat-round, segmented, with pronounced lobes, orange-brown, with a waxy coating, weighing 3-8 kg. The bark is durable. The pulp is dark orange, thick, dense, sweet, with a pleasant nutmeg aroma. Dry matter in the fruit is about 10%. Productivity up to 30 kg per plant. The value of the variety: resistance to a complex of diseases, drought resistance, attractiveness when selling fresh products on the market, suitability for long-term storage (up to 6 months, while the sweetness and aroma increase during storage) and transportation, valuable nutritional and medicinal properties. Recommended for consumption fresh, boiled, stewed, dried and dried, and for making juices [18].

Cucurbita (Dachnaya). The variety is early ripening (the period from full germination to the beginning of fruiting is 70-85 days). The plant is short-climbing and compact. The length of the main lash is average. The fruit is oval or obovate. The surface is segmented. The background color of the ripe fruit is yellow. Pattern of orange intermittent scalloped dark green stripes. The bark is medium thick, woody. The pulp is orange, medium thickness, dense, tender, sweet, juicy, with a vanilla aroma. Weight 3.5-5 kg. It is well stored (retains marketability and taste for 4 months after picking) [18].

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